

Studies on Some Haematological Parameters in Patients Diagnosed with Myasthenia Gravis at Imo State University Teaching Hospital, Orlu, Nigeria

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Abstract

Myasthenia gravis (MG) is a rare autoimmune disease characterized by fatigable weakness of the voluntary muscles and can exacerbate to life-threatening myasthenic crisis (MC), requiring intensive care treatment. This study was aimed at evaluating the levels of some haematological parameters in patients with myasthenia gravis attending neurology clinic at Imo State University Teaching Hospital, Orlu. The study employed a cross-sectional research design. The design allowed comparison levels haemoglobin (Hb), total whiteblood cell count (TWBC), and Platelets among 50 subjects which was divided into 25 myasthenia gravis patients and 25 healthy controls, aged 20-75 years. The subjects' informed consent was gotten before administering questionnaires to obtain the subjects' demographic data, medical history, life style and environmental factors that may affect the study. Two milliliters of blood samples were collected from the subjects and dispensed into ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) containers. The procedures were carried out at the hospital laboratory using standard laboratory procedures. The results of the tests were analyzed using SPSS version 27. The mean values of haemoglobin (9.24 ± 1.39)g/dl, and platelet count ($129,000 \pm 34,000.43$)/ μ l, were significantly lower in myasthenia gravis patients when compared to controls ($t=20.73$, $p=0.001$; $t=6.87$, $p=0.000$), while the mean value of TWBC (7.60 ± 2.33) cells/ μ l was significantly higher in Myasthenia gravis patients when compared to controls ($t=8.53$, $p=0.000$). There was no statistically significant increase in the mean values of Haemoglobin (9.32 ± 1.38)g/dl, TWBC (7.80 ± 2.59) and platelets ($141,600 \pm 129,050.39$) cells/ μ l in male patients with Myasthenia gravis when compared to females (9.16 ± 1.37)g/dl, (7.52 ± 20.78)cells/ μ l, and ($138,400 \pm 142,070.86$) ($t=0.41$, $p=0.683$; $t=0.37$, $p=0.715$; $t=0.76$, $p=0.649$). There was also no significant difference when the parameters were compared based on age. Myasthenia gravis is associated with decreased haemoglobin and platelet count, and an increase in TWBC count. Age and sex do not affect the above parameters in Myasthenia gravis. Therefore, supportive care is needed, such as iron or erythropoietin therapy, platelet transfusion if bleeding risk is high and antibiotics if high WBC is due to infection. Further studies should investigate autoimmune-linked cytopenias in Myasthenia gravis and thymoma-associated haematological changes in Myasthenia gravis.

Keywords: Haemoglobin, Total white blood cell, Platelet, Myasthenia gravis.

1. Introduction

Myasthenia gravis (MG) is a rare neuromuscular disease characterized by weakness and fatigue caused by binding of autoantibodies at the neuromuscular junction resulting in skeletal muscle weakness and rapid muscle fatigue (Pascuzzi and Bodkin, 2022). It affects the voluntary muscle of the body, especially those that controls the eyes, mouth throat and limbs (Brooks, 2023).

It is a chronic acquired autoimmune disorder. The autoimmune attack occurs when autoantibodies form against the nicotinic acetylcholine postsynaptic receptors at the neuromuscular junction of skeletal muscles, although the chief target of the autoimmune attack in most cases is the skeletal muscle nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR). Other antigenic

targets that are component of the neuromuscular junction (NMJ) has also been implicated (Gilhus, 2019). Myasthenia gravis can occur at any age but most frequently seen in young women (age 20-30) and men aged 50 and older, the cause of this disorder is unknown and there is no cure but early detection and prompt medical management can help people live longer and more functional lives (Spillane *et al.*, 2017). The term myasthenia gravis was first proposed in 1895 by Jolly, a German physician. Mary Walker treated a person with myasthenia gravis with physostigmine in 1934. Simpson and Nastuck detailed the autoimmune nature of the condition. In 1973, Patrick and Lindstrom used rabbits to show that immunization with purified muscle-like acetylcholine receptor caused the development of myasthenia gravis like symptoms (Gilhus, 2019).

In patients with myasthenia gravis, their hematological and biochemical parameters may be altered, potentially affecting disease and management (Akinlaja, 2016). Haemoglobin is a protein contained in the red blood cells that is responsible for carrying oxygen throughout your body tissues. To ensure adequate tissue oxygenation, a sufficient haemoglobin level must be maintained (Monga *et al.*, 2022). The amount of haemoglobin in whole blood is expressed in grams per deciliter (g/dl). The normal Hb level for males is 14 to 18 g/dl; that for females is 12 to 16 g/dl. When the haemoglobin level is low, the patient has anemia. The hematocrit measures the volume of red blood cells compared to the total blood volume (red blood cells and plasma) (Camaschella, 2021). The normal hematocrit for men is 40 to 54%; for women it is 36 to 48%. This value can be determined directly by micro hematocrit centrifugation or calculated indirectly (Saswat, 2021).

Haemoglobin carries oxygen to the muscles and reduced level may worsen muscle weakness and fatigues in an affected MG patient. It can also cause inflammation, oxidative stress, and muscle metabolism when there is any change in the haemoglobin level. White blood cells also known as leukocytes, are called immune cells or immunocytes, they are cells of the immune system that are involved in protecting the body against both infectious disease and foreign invaders. White blood cells include three main subtypes: granulocytes, lymphocytes and monocytes (Monga *et al.*, 2022). All white blood cells are produced and derived from multipotent cells in the bone marrow known as hematopoietic stem cells. The normal white cell count is usually between $4 \times 10^9/L$ and $1.1 \times 10^9/L$. In the US, this is usually expressed as 4,000 to 11,000 white blood cells per microliter of blood. White blood cells make up approximately 1% of the total blood volume in a healthy adult, white blood cell may produce antibodies that attack neuromuscular junction exacerbating the symptoms of MG in the case of immunosuppressive therapy, infection and disease severity due to an elevated WBC may influence the activity (Monga *et al.*, 2022).

Platelets have an important role in the haemostatic process. Platelets adhere to proteins exposed in the sub endothelium resulting in platelet activation, shape change, secretion from intracellular granules, and platelet aggregation which leads to sealing of the damaged vessel. Platelet counts in Myasthenia gravis (MG) can vary and may be low due to idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP); the normal platelet count is from 150,000 to 450,000 per microliter of blood (Fritz and Speroff, 2020).

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Study Area

This study was conducted at the Imo State Teaching Hospital, Orlu, which is a tertiary health care institution that provides specialized medical services to patients from Orlu and its surroundings. The hospital has various departments, including neurology, hematology biochemistry, and laboratory medicine, which will be involved in this study. The study accessed the hospital's patient population diagnosed with myasthenia gravis and being managed at the neurology unit, the laboratory facilities where the hematological and biochemical test was analyzed and medical records, which was to enable the collection and analysis of data.

2.2 Study Design

The study employed a cross sectional research design. The design biochemical parameters among (50) subjects which was divided into (25) myasthenia gravis patients and (25) healthy controls. The subjects for the study included both males and females aged 20-75 years. The subjects' informed consent was gotten before administering questionnaires to obtain the subjects' demographic data, medical history, life style and environmental factors that may affect this study.

2mls of blood was collected and dispensed into EDTA tubes for the estimation of the haematological parameters and statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 27, to allow an objective investigation of the association between Myasthenia gravis and various parameters by observing and recording the parameters without intervening or manipulating the patients' treatment.

2.3 Study Population

The study population comprised of diagnosed Myasthenia gravis patients attending the neurology clinic at Imo State University Teaching Hospital (IMSUTH). Both male and female adult subjects of age group 20-75 years and age-matched healthy controls without myasthenia gravis or any other neurological disorder associated with age, gender and demographic characteristics. A total of fifty individuals participated in this study. They were divided into two (2) groups,

test groups (myasthenia gravis) and control group (healthy subject). The test group included fifty (25) MG patients, and fifty (25) healthy subjects residing in Orlu metropolis, Imo State.

2.4 Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the research ethical committee (REC) of Imo State University Teaching Hospital (IMSUTH), Orlu. All participants who gave their informed consent were enrolled in the study and samples were collected.

2.5 Sample Collection

Two milliliters (2 mls) of venous blood sample was collected from patients with myasthenia gravis and healthy control subjects and dispensed into EDTA tubes for estimating the haematological parameters.

3. Laboratory Analysis

The determination of haemoglobin, total white blood cell and platelet counts were done using Laser-based flow cytometry.

4. Statistical Analysis

All the statistical analysis was done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) software system. Statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation and Students independent t-test was used. The probability value less than 0.05 was used and considered significant.

5. Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Data of Myasthenia gravis Patients and Control.

From the data in table 1, majority of the patients with Myasthenia gravis were above the age of 50 years as the 44% of the recruited patients with the disease were within that age range. Females recorded the highest number of the disease, 52%, while the males with the disease were 48%. With regards to marital status, 40% of both married and divorced subjects had Myasthenia gravis, while singles recorded the least distribution. And lastly, artisans recorded the highest number of patients with Myasthenia gravis (32%).

Variable	Myasthenia gravis Patients N (%)	Control N (%)
Age (yrs)		
20– 30	2 (8%)	4 (16%)
31– 40	5 (20%)	6 (24%)
41– 50	7 (28%)	3 (12%)
>50	11 (44%)	12 (48%)
Total	25	25
Gender		
Male	12 (48%)	11 (44%)
Female	13 (52%)	14 (56%)
Total	25	25
Marital Status		
Single	5 (20%)	4 (16%)
Married	10 (40%)	12 (48%)
Divorced	10 (40%)	9 (36%)
Total	25	25
Occupation		
Student	6 (24%)	3 (12%)
Civil servant	7 (28%)	5 (20%)
Trader	4 (16%)	3 (12%)
Artisan	8 (32%)	14 (56%)
Total	25	25

Table 2: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, Total White Blood Cell and Platelet counts in Myasthenia Gravis Patients and Non-Myasthenia Gravis Subjects.

The mean values of haemoglobin (9.24 ± 1.39)g/dl, and platelet count ($129,000 \pm 34,000.43$)/ μ l, were significantly lower in myasthenia gravis patients when compared to controls ($t=20.73$, $p=0.001$; $t=6.87$, $p=0.000$) while the mean value of TWBC (7.6 ± 23.28)cells/ μ l was significantly higher in Myasthenia gravis patients when compared to controls ($t=8.53$, $p=0.000$).

Parameter	Test	Control	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	9.24±1.36	15.16±1.49	20.73	0.001*
TWBC (cells/ μ l)	7.64±2.33	4.70±0.74	8.53	0.000*
Platelet (cells/ μ l)	129,000±34,000.43	164,600±94,600.86	6.87	0.000*

KEY:

Hb: Haemoglobin

TWBC: Total White Blood Cell Count

*: Significant p value

Table 3: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, TWBC, and Platelets in Male Versus Female Patients with Myasthenia Gravis.

There was no statistically significant increase in the mean values of Haemoglobin (9.32±1.38)g/dl, TWBC(7.80± 2.59) and platelets (141,600±129,050.39) cells/ μ l in male patients with Myasthenia gravis when compared to females (9.16±1.37)g/dl, (7.52±2.08)cells/ μ l, and (138,400±142,070.86) (t=0.41, p=0.683; t=0.37, p=0.715; t=0.76, p=0.649).

Parameter	Male	Female	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	9.32±1.38	9.16±1.37	0.41	0.683
TWBC (cells/ μ l)	7.77±2.59	7.52±2.08	0.37	0.715
Platelet (cells/ μ l)	141,600±129,050.39	138,400±142,070.86	0.76	0.649

KEY:

TWBC: Total White Blood Cell Count

*: Significant p value

Table 4: Comparison of the Mean Values of Haemoglobin, TWBC, and Platelets in Myasthenia gravis Patients of Ages 20-40 years verses >40-70 years.

There was no significant difference in the mean values of haemoglobin, TWBC and platelets, in patients with Myasthenia gravis of ages (20-40) years when compared to patients with Myasthenia gravis of ages (>40) yrs (t=0.64, p=0.528; t=0.88, p=0.383 and t=0.75, p=0.548).

Parameter	(20-40)yrs	(>40)yrs	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	9.41±1.66	9.15±1.20	0.64	0.528
TWBC (cells/ μ l)	7241.18±2342.56	7854.55±2330.11	0.88	0.383
Platelet (cells/ μ l)	131,760±87,150.64	140,438±111,328.78	0.75	0.548

KEY:

TWBC: Total White Blood Cell Count

*: Significant

5. Discussion

Myasthenia gravis (MG) constitutes a chronic, autoimmune disorder with a step-wise progression of symptoms and involvement of multiple complex pathophysiological pathways (Punga *et al.*, 2022). The diseases have been reported to have an effect on the haematological parameters (Huijbers *et al.*, 2022).

In this study the age group >50 recorded the highest number of patients with myasthenia gravis, females also recorded a greater percentage of individuals with the disease, while married couples and artisan recorded the highest frequency distribution of the disease. The result is in agreement with findings of Giannoccaro *et al.*, (2022), who reported a similar finding.

In the present study, the mean value of haemoglobin was significantly lower in Myasthenia gravis Patient when compared to controls. Many studies indicated that Myasthenia gravis affects the absorption of iron at the gastrointestinal tract, which in turn leads to iron deficiency anaemia, hence the reason for the low level of haemoglobin in Myasthenia gravis patients. The result is in agreement with the findings of Burns *et al.*, (2018), who reported that anaemia was common in Myasthenia gravis. They further stated that the proton-pump inhibitors and histamine-2 receptor antagonists that are often used in conjunction with prednisolone are a frequently overlooked cause of impaired iron absorption in

patients with the disease, thereby causing anaemia. According to Gelinas *et al.*, (2022), pure red cell aplasia is occasionally observed in patients with thymoma-associated MG.

The current study reveals that the mean value of TWBC was significantly higher in Myasthenia gravis patients when compared to controls. The increase in total white blood cell count in Myasthenia gravis patients might be as a result of inflammation. Cytokine producing role of nearly all immune cells is known; however, FcR-expressing monocytes/macrophages are the primary sources of the proinflammatory/inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, including mainly TNF, IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, and IL-12 causing histopathological injuries in target tissues, autoantigen expressions, and autoantibody production in MG and other autoimmune diseases (Uzawa *et al.*, 2021). The findings from this study is consistent with the study carried out by Aricha *et al.*, (2021), who reported that monocytes and macrophages are raised in Myasthenia gravis patients, they further stated monocytes and other cell types bind to TLR4 of monocytes and macrophages and induce enhanced production of TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, macrophage inflammatory protein (MIP), C-reactive protein (CRP) and others to amplify inflammatory responses.

In this study, the mean value of platelet count was significantly reduced in patients with Myasthenia gravis when compared to controls. The decrease might be as a result of the auto-antibodies causing a destruction of the platelet cell count leading to reduced level. The finding from this study is consistent with the study carried out by Giannoccaro *et al.*, (2022), who reported that in patients with myasthenia gravis, auto antibodies attack the platelet cell causing a reduced number of platelet count.

This study showed that there was a non-significant difference in the mean values of haemoglobin, TWBC and platelets in myasthenia gravis patients when compared based on age and sex. The result is consistent with the finding of Aricha *et al.*, (2021), who reported that age and sex of the patients suffering from myasthenia gravis are no indicative factors in the determination of haematological parameters.

6. Conclusion

Myasthenia gravis is associated with decreased levels of haemoglobin, and platelet count, with an increase in total white blood cell count. Age and sex of subjects with myasthenia gravis have no relationship with haematological parameters.

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